

THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES BASED WITH COMPOSITE COLUMN CORES

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ABSTRACT

Composite sandwich structures containing high-performance core materials based on vertical composite columns have been manufactured using a lost-mold technique. The structures were prepared by drilling holes at specific locations through a dissolvable mold block. Long carbon fiber strands were then inserted into each of the holes, ensuring that one continuous tow extended through all of the vertical elements within a given core structure. Two threading techniques were used to prepare the composite columns. One resulted in the horizontal fibers extending along the inner surfaces of the composite facings and the other involved weaving the fibers through the composite facing. Both methods offered the advantage that the fibers formed part of the upper and lower skins. Following infusion with epoxy resin, using the VARTM manufacturing procedure, individual specimens were removed from the blocks in preparation for subsequent compression testing. The results were compared with an FE model which showed good agreement in terms of predicting the modulus of elasticity and peak stress.

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is a strong interest in developing lightweight, high-performance structures for enhanced aerospace design. Traditionally, many lightweight aircraft components have been based on sandwich structures, consisting of composite skins bonded to honeycomb or foam cores. More recently, there has been a growing interest in the use of foldcore structures and lightweight lattice architectures for use in aerospace design. The unique and attractive properties offered by cellular materials based on lattice truss topologies have, in recent years, been investigated by a number of authors [1-6]. One particular area of interest relates to those structures whose members deform in stretching-dominated, rather than bending-dominated response modes. Previous work has shown that such lattices exhibit stiffness and strength properties that scale linearly with density, ρ . This is in contrast to polymer and metal foams whose strength and stiffness properties scale as $\rho^{3/2}$ and ρ^2 respectively. Queheillalt and Wadley [1] investigated the compressive properties of pyramidal lattice truss structures with hollow sections and compared their response to an equivalent solid truss structure. They showed that the compression strength of the hollow sections was approximately double that of a solid pyramidal lattice of similar density. Deshpande [4] investigated the properties of the stretching-dominated octet-truss lattice structures that were manufactured by stacking layers of pre-fabricated triangulated layers and tetrahedral cores together. The authors concluded that octet-truss type structures offer significant potential for use in lightweight design. In a subsequent study, Wang [3] investigated the performance of panels based on a 3D Kagomé core structure. The authors produced truss panels in which the members were manufactured from a copper alloy using an investment-casting process. Unfortunately, following testing, many of the samples highlighted the presence of localised porosity associated with the casting process.

To date almost all lattice structures have been manufactured from either metallic materials or plastic. However, in a novel study, Finnegan and co-workers [6] investigated the compressive properties of carbon fiber-based truss structures. Composite-based lattice structures offer enormous potential given that they potentially offer extremely high values of strength at a low density. This is most clearly demonstrated in the 'Ashby' diagram shown in Figure 1 [6].

Figure 1: An Ashby strength versus density map for engineering materials [6].

Here, the dashed line suggests that carbon fibre-based lattice structures can approach the limit of the unattainable materials space. If such materials could successfully be produced, it would open up a new front in the manufacture of lightweight structures for the aircraft and space industries. Finnegan and co-workers attempted to manufacture a range of carbon/epoxy pyramidal structures. A number of approaches were investigated. Initially, pultruded rods were bonded to the face sheets containing a series of pre-drilled holes. Following this, truss patterns were cut from unidirectional sheets and adhesively bonded into milled slots in the skins. These procedures were rejected as a result of premature failure of the bonds. A third technique proved more successful. Here, a semi-continuous truss pattern was cut from $0^{\circ}, 90^{\circ}$ panels using a water-jet cutting facility. The pyramidal structure was then formed by snap-fitting the members together and the skins were then bonded. Here, although impressive, it is clear that the measured values fall below the limit associated with the unattainable materials space. This discrepancy was attributed to the inefficient use of material in the nodes and the onset of delamination from the nodal connections.

The aim of this research paper is to use a lost-mold technique for producing lattice structures of varying complexity. Attention in particular is given to assessing the effect of fiber volume fraction, strut diameter and lattice design on the compression properties of the structures.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Manufacture of the Composite Cores

The composite column cores were manufactured using a lost mold/core procedure. Here, a series of vertical holes were drilled into core blocks with length, width and thickness dimensions of 150 x 90 x 36 mm respectively. Four drill diameters were used, these being 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 and 4.0 mm. Here, 2 mm and 2.5 mm diameter holes were drilled in six by six arrays, the 3 mm holes in six by five arrays and the 4 mm holes in five by four arrays. Carbon fiber tows were then threaded through the holes in order to reinforce the structure in the through-thickness direction. Two weaving patterns were adopted. The first procedure involved threading the fibers through the array of holes and then across the top of the core block. It is worth noting that the same fiber tow is used to link the adjacent holes, ensuring that there are no fiber breaks in the through-thickness reinforcements. The fiber volume fraction within an individual hole was varied by using increasing numbers of fiber tows during the threading process. The second weaving pattern involved threading the fibers through the carbon fiber fabric used to produce the facings in the resulting sandwich structures. Tying the through-thickness fibers to the

facings has the effect of reducing lateral movement of the composite columns during the compression process.

Following the threading process, the reinforced core blocks were infused with resin using the VARTM manufacturing technique. Here, a distribution or flow medium, Gurit Knitflow40[®], was used at the top facesheet to facilitate the flow of resin throughout the structure. The resin used to infuse the fibrous structure was two-part toughened epoxy, Prime[™] 20LV, with a fast hardener, supplied by Gurit Ltd. A glass mold, with line injection and a line vent was used to fabricate the lattice structures. The glass mold permitted the observation of resin flow process in the lower skin during the infusion process. The skins in the sandwich structures were based on four layers of carbon fiber fabric. The edges of the mold were sealed using a vacuum bagging material and a sealant tape. The mold was then infused with resin under vacuum at a pressure of 1 atm. The panels were allowed to cure at room temperature for approximately 12 hours and then post-cured at 65 °C for 7 hours.

2.2 Compression Tests

The compression strengths of the composite cores were measured by loading the square specimens between two circular steel platens at a crosshead displacement rate of 2 mm/min. Typically, three repeat tests were conducted on each core structure. The failure modes during compression loading were elucidated by photographing the samples at regular intervals.

3 NUMERICAL MODELING

A numerical investigation of the proposed core structures was performed in order to predict the response of the vertical column cores under quasi-static loading. A series of finite element models have been created using the ANSYS FE package and the predictions compared with experimental results. Two finite element models were created; one using three-dimensional Solid185 homogeneous solid elements, and another using 3-D 2-Node Beam188 elements. Solid185 is defined by eight nodes having three degrees of freedom at each node: translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions, while Beam188 is based on Timoshenko beam theory [7].

Both elements support failure criteria based on material strength limits, damage onset with Hashin failure criteria, and damage evolution based on continuum damage mechanics method (CDM). Hashin failure criteria was selected due to its ability to distinguish between fiber and matrix failure due to compressive and tensile loads in the longitudinal and transverse directions as described below.

In the Hashin criterion, tensile and compressive loads in the fiber direction are predicted with the expression [7],

$$\xi = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_{xt}^f} \right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{xy}^2 + \sigma_{xz}^2}{(\sigma_{xy}^f)^2} & \text{if } \sigma_x > 0 \\ \left(\frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_{xc}^f} \right)^2 & \text{if } \sigma_x \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

On the other hand, Hashin Matrix Failure Criterion is governed as follows [7],

$$\xi = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\sigma_y + \sigma_z}{\sigma_{yt}^f} \right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{yz}^2 - \sigma_z \sigma_y}{(\sigma_{yz}^f)^2} + \frac{\sigma_{xy}^2 + \sigma_{xz}^2}{(\sigma_{xy}^f)^2} & \text{if } \sigma_y + \sigma_z > 0 \\ \left[\frac{1}{\sigma_{yc}^f} \left(\frac{\sigma_{yc}^f}{2\sigma_{yz}^f} \right)^2 - 1 \right] (\sigma_y + \sigma_z) + \left(\frac{\sigma_y + \sigma_z}{2\sigma_{yz}^f} \right)^2 + \frac{\sigma_{yz}^2 - \sigma_z \sigma_y}{(\sigma_{yz}^f)^2} + \frac{\sigma_{xy}^2 + \sigma_{xz}^2}{(\sigma_{xy}^f)^2} & \text{if } \sigma_y + \sigma_z \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

The most critical of the failure modes is selected. Where, σ_{xt}^f and σ_{xc}^f are the longitudinal tensile and compressive strength loads. σ_{yt}^f and σ_{yc}^f are the transverse tensile and compressive strength loads. σ_{xy}^f and σ_{yz}^f are the in plane and out of plane shear strength respectively.

The response of the material after damage initiation (which describes the rate of degradation of the material stiffness once the initiation criterion is satisfied) is defined by the following equation [8]:

$$[\sigma] = [D]_d \varepsilon$$

Where: σ = effective stress averaged over the entire domain. ε = total elastic strain and $[D]_d$ = damaged elasticity matrix. The $[D]_d$ matrix is equivalent to the compliance matrix with its diagonal terms divided by $(1 - d)$ where d is a damage variable with valid values between 0 and 1, where 0 = no damage and 1 = complete loss of stiffness in the affected mode.

A single unit cell was modelled, results of single column can be extrapolated for any array set of columns through linear scaling. The model setup including loading and boundary conditions on a single unit cell for both, solid and beam models are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Solid and beam model setup.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Influence of Weave Method

A single experimental stress-strain curve was chosen which is representative of the average for each configuration using both weaving patterns is illustrated in Figure 3. In terms of peak load and energy absorption (by integrating the area under the load-displacement curve) it is clear that weave pattern B outperforms pattern A. It is worth noting that Weave pattern (A) specimens generally failed at the column/skin connection point, as the strength of this juncture is governed by the strength of matrix holding them together. Consequently, once the node fails, the core was free to move laterally resulting in unstable behavior.

Figure 3: Stress-strain traces of individual columns (a) 2.5 mm diameter (b) 3mm diameter and (c) 4mm diameter and Stress-strain traces of multiple columns (d) 2.5 mm diameter (e) 3mm diameter and (f) 4mm diameter

As observed with the individual columns, the weave pattern method has a significant influence on the peak stress and the post yield behavior in terms of energy absorption. Tying the through-thickness fibers to the facings has the effect of reducing lateral movement of the composite core resulting in a more efficient use of the core material. This is elucidated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Weave pattern influence on load bearing capability
(a) Diameter = 4mm (b) Diameter = 3mm

All columns arranged in arrays had a fiber volume fraction of approximately 28% the results of which are summarized in Figure 5 in terms of peak stress and specific energy absorption (SEA)

Figure 5: a) Peak stress vs. column diameter. b) Specific Energy Absorption SEA vs. column diameter.

4.2 Influence of Column Diameter

The influence of geometry (column diameter) while holding the fiber volume content within the columns, at 42% in this case, is examined in Figure 6. The thinnest columns having a diameter of 2mm failed due to global buckling while the 4mm exhibited progressive crushing fracture mechanism, while intermediate samples exhibited a mixture between global and micro buckling. It is clear that the diameter influences peak load and failure mechanism. It is possible to estimate the buckling compressive stress using the Euler buckling equation. However, the general Euler buckling formula is developed for isotropic materials and subsequently modified to account for the influence of material orthotropy as follows [8],

$$\sigma_{critical} = \frac{\pi^2 E_x}{SR^2 + 1.2\pi^2 \left(\frac{E_x}{G_{xz}} \right)}$$

where,

SR: Slenderness ratio = Specimen effective length (L_e) / Radius of gyration (R),

$L_e = KL$, K: end constraint (assume $K=1$), L= specimen length (mm), and

$R = \sqrt{\frac{I}{A}}$, I: moment of inertia (mm^4), A: cross sectional area (mm^2).

E_x = axial stiffness in the direction of compressive loading

G_{xz} = shear stiffness in the through-the-thickness direction ($G_{xz} = G_{xy}$ for transversely isotropic material).

Figure 6: Influence of geometry on failure mode

Referring to Figure 7, Euler buckling is the dominant failure mode for columns with SR above 50. Between a SR of 50-45 the failure deviates from the predicted Euler buckling load and fails due to micro buckling/progressive crushing as the applied load approaches the material strength limit. The figure contains experimental, analytical as well as FEA based on the solid model results that show good agreement. FEA results for both solid and beam elements showed very close agreement (less than 3% variation on average).

Figure 7: Experimental, Analytical and FEA results

Specific Energy Absorption (SEA) obtained by dividing the area under the load-displacement curve by the specimen mass and results are summarized in Figure 8. Specimens that fail due to geometric instability (Euler buckling) exhibit the lowest SEA, while samples that fail due to microbuckling / progressive crushing exhibit higher SEA values as they make more efficient use of the material.

Figure 8: Specific Energy Absorption, SEA at different fiber volume fraction

Figure 9: Stress-strain traces of individual columns (a) 2 mm diameter CFRP rods (b) 2.5mm diameter CFRP rods (c) 3mm CFRP rods and (d) 4mm CFRP rods. The dashed lines correspond to the experimental curves and the solid lines to the numerical predictions.

FEA using solid elements yielded results that were with 3% of results obtained using beam elements as previously mentioned. However, the computation cost of using beam elements significantly lower than its counterpart solid element. Beam element models are computationally efficient and capable of capturing the progressive damage evolution based on continuous damage evolution post failure. Results from FEA models show good agreement with experimental data as illustrated in Figure 9 for individual columns and Figure 10 for arrays of columns.

Figure 10: Stress-strain traces of column arrays of 2 mm diameter array and 4mm diameter array. The dashed lines correspond to the experimental curves and the solid lines to the numerical predictions.

5 CONCLUSION

A series of individual and arrays of vertical columns were manufactured using the lost mold technique. Two weaving methods were utilized during the manufacturing procedure. Compression tests revealed that weaving the fibers through the core and over the facesheets provided lateral stability and consequently improved peak stress and energy absorption characteristics. Samples with slenderness ratios above 50 failed due to global buckling and analytical predictions based on the Euler buckling for orthotropic material showed good agreement with experimental results. As the slenderness ratio decreases below 50 other failure mechanisms are triggered (microbuckling and progressive crushing) as the applied compressive load approaches the material strength limits. FEA based on Hashin failure criteria was carried out and results showed good agreement with experimental data.

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